

A COMPUTER SYSTEM FOR LIFECYCLE COST ESTIMATION AND MANUFACTURABILITY ASSESSMENT OF COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The aim of this paper is to describe a computer based system that i) determines how a composite component should be manufactured, ii) measures the complexities of the part (based on a model verified at MIT [2,8,10]), and then iii) estimates the cost of manufacturing the component. The computer system architecture centers on cost, process, and manufacturability knowledge stored in a database that is accumulated, stored and then retrieved for future usage. This paper will describe the overall design of the computer system using object oriented analysis and design (OOA&D). The paper will show how to represent manufacturing knowledge in a computer based system, and also demonstrate how to store and retrieve a suggested processing tree for a given component, key aspects of the database design. Recent developments in object oriented technology, patterns and patterns language[3] will also be discussed in this paper.

KEYWORDS: cost estimation, manufacturing, object-oriented database management system

INTRODUCTION

Lifecycle costs and manufacturability are today the key aspects of large composite components. Much of the high cost associated with composites results when the specifications for the product do not correspond with the capabilities of the manufacturing processes. Therefore, in the composites industry, there is a need to develop the ability to evaluate new concepts and designs on the basis of their manufacturability along with their structural integrity and other measures of performance. There is also a need to integrate the preliminary structural design with the proposed manufacturing approach to minimise the cost and duration of development.

The aim of our project is to develop a computer based system to i) determine how a composite component should be manufactured, ii) measure the complexities of the part (based on a model verified at MIT[2,8,10]) and iii) estimate the cost of manufacturing the component. The system will also be used to evaluate alternative designs for a component so that the most effective design, in terms of manufacturability and lifecycle costs, could be utilised.

This paper will describe the overall design of the computer system using object oriented analysis and design(OOA&D). "Object-oriented" means that software is organised as a collection of discrete objects that incorporate both data structure and behaviour [6]. Both the Rumbaugh [6] and the Booch methodologies [5](software engineering techniques) will be applied in this paper. An object oriented database system (OODBMS) is used to store and retrieve objects, even very complex objects such as those found in composite manufacturing

(for example, an aircraft undercarriage door and its associated manufacturing procedures and resources). Patterns and patterns languages [3] will also be discussed in this paper as expert, masterful, software designs for real, difficult problems in computer representation. Patterns are the key to an approach to the challenges in representation that are inherent to the problem of lifecycle cost estimation and manufacturability assessment.

METHODOLOGY

Object Oriented Database Management Systems (OODBMS)

An OODBMS is a system that can store, retrieve, and manipulate objects that directly model or reflect physical objects in the real world. OODBMS keep the object [4] data, but also store behaviour, and relationships between objects. For certain kinds of applications, for example manufacturing, this is a significant advantage over relational databases. Real objects, for example machines, have behaviour. Objects are also related to each other through inheritance (specialisation), association, and aggregation (containment) relationships. An OODBMS has the ability to maintain all this information in an integrated fashion.

Figure 1. The Difference between Object Oriented and Relational Databases

An OODBMS is event-driven compared with a RDBMS (Relational DBMS) which is value-driven. The difference is shown in Figure 1. All the operations can be stored with the objects, eg. set and update operations; this models what happens in the real world. Users and software engineers do not need to specify such operations outside the OODBMS. An RDBMS is different because only the data(table) are stored; users have to figure out the relationships or the path to the behaviour. This makes the computer representations very complicated, and some representations may be impossible.

An OODBMS has both the benefits of a conventional database, like persistence, concurrency, change management, recovery and security, and the advantages of object-oriented technology, such as encapsulation, inheritance, polymorphism, reusability, etc.

Patterns and Pattern Languages

The computer system described in this paper addresses a complicated area of manufacturing. For this application, computer representation is important because we need to represent

complex relationships between objects, such as different resources and different manufacturing processes. Patterns in software engineering describe tested software engineering solutions to particular problems.

A pattern language defines a collection of patterns and the rules to combine them. Pattern languages describe software frameworks or families of related systems. Patterns and pattern languages are ways to describe good designs. In this project, patterns have been used to address particularly challenging areas with reusable, portable, and extensible object oriented software.

Notation

The notation we use here is the OMT (Object Modeling Technique, developed by Rumbaugh[6]) notation.(Figure 2).

Figure 2. Object Notation

System Overview

The system is depicted in Figure 3, in a use case representation. A use case diagram indicates use cases (ways the system can be used), actors (users in certain roles), and relationships between use cases and actors. The main subsystems are the following:

- CAD System(MicroStation™)
- Patran™ P3 Laminate Modeller
- Complexity Analysis
- Manufacturing Plan Generation
- Manufacturing Cost Estimation
- Database (ObjectStore®)

There are three levels to the computer system from the architectural point of view. The first level is the Manufacturing Cost Estimation, which calculates the cost. The cost is related to the processing tree which is also associated with the component complexity. Different process fabrications yield different costs and use different complexities, this is the second level: Complexity Analysis and Manufacturing Plan Generation. In a composite component, we not only have the geometric information, which includes dimensions and tolerances, but also the laminate complexities. The sources of all this information are the CAD System and the Laminate Modeller, which is the third level of this system. MicroStation™ 95 is chosen as the CAD System. The Patran™ P3 Laminate Modeller uses IGES files from the CAD system for

modeling. All these three levels make up the system. This paper concentrates on the first and second levels (described in the following sections), while Kumar’s paper[7] describes level 3 in detail.

Figure 3. Use Case Representation of the Computer System

MANUFACTURING PLAN GENERATION

Manufacturing Process Representation

A manufacturing plan is made up of processes, and every process has its own resources. Equipment is a kind of resource, so are labor, tool, composite tool, and even a compound resource (a set of multiple resources that are always used together). The Composite pattern [3] is applied to represent all these resources. The Composite pattern “composes objects into tree structures to represent part-whole hierarchies. It also lets clients treat individual objects and compositions of objects uniformly.”[3]. The key to this pattern is an abstract class[4] *Resource* (Figure 4, using the notation provided in Figure 2) that represents both primitives, such as *Equipment*, *Labor*, *Non_Composite_Tool*, and *Compound Resource*. A *Compound Resource* is not only the aggregation of *Resource*, it is inherited from or specialises *Resource* as well. That means a compound resource is a resource. By using this pattern, users can group the resources to form a compound resource, which in turn can be grouped to form still more complex resource recursively. (The Composite pattern is used in other aspects of the computer system, for example compound components.)

Figure 4. The Manufacturing Process Representation

Process has *Resource*, *Material*, process name, ID and strategy to calculate the time spent on this process as shown in Figure 4. The *Process* class uses *Cost_Equation* class as the strategy to calculate the cost (Fig 4). There are six equations according to the MIT model [2]. All the equations are inherited[4] from the *Cost_Equation* class. This makes all these equations have the same interface, and makes our system more flexible as any new ways to calculate cost can be easily added. This design uses the Strategy pattern [3].

Processing Tree Representation

The processing tree representation is also shown in Figure 4. A *Processing Tree* is an aggregation of *Process*. It has *name*, *ID* and a *process list* (or, more accurately a graph) which holds all the processes. *Processing Tree* has behaviours. For example, *Add()* provides a way to add a new process to the processing tree for a component, *Remove()* can be used to delete a process from an exist processing plan, *GetProcessList()* iterates over the processing tree, and *TotalTime()* supplies the method to calculate the total manufacturing time of the component. The database stores the processing trees for the various components which can be retrieved later on to generate a processing plan for a new or similar part. The pseudo code for entering, retrieving and generating a processing tree for a component can be shown below:

1. `open_database();`
2. `query_and_select_process_from_database();`
3. `process=pick_up_process(ID);`
4. `processing_tree=add_process_to_processing_tree(process);`
5. `add_processing_tree_to_container();`
6. `close_database();`

First, open the database (1), then query and select the process for a new component (2), then go to the database to pick up the process by ID number or any of its properties (3), after that, add all the necessary processes in the processing tree (4), store this processing tree in a container of the database (5), and finally save into the database by closing the database (6). Because tooling for a composite or laminate component is almost as complicated as the component itself, we mention it here explicitly. Basically there are two kinds of tooling. One is non composite (metal), and we regard this as a resource. The other is composite tool, and we think of this as another composite component that must be manufactured.

COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS AND COST ESTIMATION

Manufacturing Cost Estimation

The aim of this project is to estimate the cost of manufacturing the component. For each of the manufacturing steps, the cost considerations are materials; resources, which include the cost of equipment, labor, tool, and floor space; labor time, which is related to extensible parameters or measurements of the component; and complexities of the process that are significant cost drivers. A cost model for composite manufacturing should incorporate measures that a designer can easily obtain.

The *Material* class is for materials, see Figure 4, with cost or price as an attribute. Once geometric and complexity measurements have been made and stored in the database, we can call the operation in the material class to calculate the cost.

CAD Translation and Complexity Measurements

The CAD system used for the analysis is MicroStationTM 95, chosen for its ease of use. The design models can easily be exported from and imported to any other CAD systems by the use of the standard Initial Graphics Exchange Specification (IGES). MicroStationTM provides access to the extensible parameters or measurements, such as dimensions, surface area, volume, etc. These parameters are then written into the database [7].

The most important geometric complexity is the curvature angle of the part. This is determined using the PatranTM Laminate Modeller. The Laminate Modeller generates files that give the weft and warp coordinates of the fibres. The curvature bend angle can be numerically calculated from the knowledge of warp and weft fibres. The fibre orientation and ply count can also be read from the files that are generated in the PatranTM Laminate Modeller. Laminate complexities can be calculated with knowledge of extensible parameters, fibre orientation angle, and ply count. All of this geometric and laminate complexity information can then be stored in the database, and be queried when calculating the cost or time of a process for a component.

Another complexity of the part is determined by the sum of the dimensions required to describe the part and the tolerances on those dimensions. We consider these dimensions and tolerances as another complexity metric. This simpler approach could be used for fairly rapid comparison of alternative designs.

PROCESSING COST

In terms of processing cost, we take equipment, labour, tools and compound resource into account, with labor and processing cost dependent on the estimated time to process a given part. The time required to complete a processing step is related to the extensible parameters and complexities of the part. Extensible parameters are length, surface area, weight, volume, etc., and various manufacturing processes scale with certain extensible parameters. For instance, the time for hand layup is proportional to the surface area of the part. If the part has a complex shape, the linear or simple measurement is not sufficient, and MIT's approach [8] determines the amount of information required to represent a complex shape. Complexity can then be measured by an information metric [8].

There are six cost equations (two examples are provided in equations 1 and 2 in Figure 5) which take all these into consideration. The equation class is shown in Figure 4, and *Process* object uses *CostEquation* when calculating the processing time.

$$\text{Minutes} = \left[\left(\frac{\text{Setup}}{\text{Run}} \right) + \left(\frac{\text{Delay}}{\text{Operation}} \right) \left(\frac{\text{Operations}}{\text{Run}} \right) \right] \frac{(\text{Parts/Shipset})}{(\text{Parts/Lot})(\text{Lots/Run})} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Minutes} = \left[\left(\frac{\text{Setup}}{\text{Run}} \right) + \left\{ \left(\frac{\text{Delay}}{\text{Operation}} \right) + \sqrt{\left(\frac{V_1}{v_{o1}} \right)^2 + \frac{2t_1 V_1}{v_{o1}}} \right\} \left(\frac{\text{Operations}}{\text{Run}} \right) \right] \frac{(\text{Parts/Shipset})}{(\text{Lots/Run})(\text{Parts/Lot})} \quad (2)$$

Figure 5. Two Sample Cost Equations

Learning Curve Effects

Learning curves must be taken into account. They are expressible by the number of parts made when the time per part levels off and stops decreasing significantly. This effect is for a new part, a new process, or a new labourer. Learning curve can also impact material scrap rates. We consider these learning curves as additional database objects.

CASE STUDY

We are investigating an airplane undercarriage door design as a case study for the computer based cost estimation system. This undercarriage door is a redesign, and the investigation involves comparing the new design to the original one. Our objective is to estimate the cost for the two new different designs, comparing them both to the old design.

The new cocured stiffened design involves the following processing steps:

- Layup the exterior skin over the main tool
- Put honeycomb with template
- Layup the ribs and spars
- Layup the interior skin
- Cure the whole part

Figure 6. Sample massaging for Undercarriage Door Cost Estimation

The event trace of a scenario (Figure 6) describes how the system would be used for this case study. The text on the top of each vertical line is the class[4] name, which can be found from Figure 4, a horizontal arrow line indicates a message or behaviour between two objects, and a little rectangular box on a vertical line stands for an operation of the class that would be carried out in response to the message.

First of all, we instantiate and store the resources which are used to manufacture the component. We open the database (message 1), and instantiate or create all the instances that

are not already in the database, such as equipment (Gerber Cut and Core Cover), and labourers (Manager and Inspector), from resource class *Resource* (message 2). Then, we put all these resources in *Resource_Container* (message 3), which is a container of the database. All these resource objects are stored in the database by message 4.

Second, we install any needed processes into the database, making objects of class *Process* (message 5), such as “layup manual prepreg fabric”, “cure autoclave”, “position manual mylar template”. With resources, only processes that are not already present in the database must be instantiated, and the parameters are initialised when the processes are created. Then all these processes are placed in the *Process_Container* of the database (message 6). Finally we store all the process information into the database, this is message 7. Similar operations are carried out for the *Material* class, setting cost parameters to take material cost into account.

Third, we generate the processing plan for this component (These steps would be required whenever a new processing tree is under consideration and must therefore be added to the database). We get the *Process_Container* from the database (message 8), and next instantiate the class *ProcessingTree* to hold the processing plan for our undercarriage door (message 9). Then we can select and pick up all the processes we need for the component from the *Process_Container* (message 10). At this stage, we should take the complexity information into account, querying and therefore obtaining this information from the database for the appropriate process (detailed in [7]). After that, we add the processes to the *ProcessingTree* object (message 11), then we install this processing tree for the undercarriage door (message 12) and close the database (message 13).

If all the processing information was already stored in the ObjectStore[®] database, we could estimate the cost of manufacturing the component merely by querying and picking up the processing tree from the database. Then, the cost estimation would be accomplished by the processing tree calling its *TotalTime()* operation, which in turn calls the *get_time()* operation of each process.

CONCLUSION

The MIT model for cost estimation [2] has been the basis for this computer based system. The comparison with Australian data has been reported, but additional comparisons are ongoing. While the cost estimation is done automatically, the manufacturing process plan generation is done manually. This means we need to query the process database manually, under the direction of a manufacturing expert, in order to generate the manufacturing plan. Semi-automatic plan generation is our next step. It will allow for some steps in the processing tree to be copied or repeated for a new component that is similar to an existing one. More automated processing tree generation may be possible by “intelligent” retrieval and extension according to the part’s complexity and specification.

Through the case study, we have been applying object oriented technology to aerospace composite manufacturability successfully. The benefits of this approach, as compared to a relational database, are extensibility and reusability. These issues will become important as new components, new processes, and additional lifecycle costs are considered. And, an object oriented approach is necessary for addressing manufacturability.

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